

AI models for demographic prediction in e-commerce: age and gender from initial user interactions

Javier De Andrés¹, Daniel Fernandez-Lanvin²,
Martin Gonzalez-Rodriguez² and Beatriz Pariente-Martinez²

¹ Department of Accounting, Universidad de Oviedo, Oviedo, Asturias, Spain

² Department of Computer Science, Universidad de Oviedo, Oviedo, Asturias, Spain

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the feasibility of inferring key demographic features, specifically gender and age, from analyzing the performance of fundamental interactive tasks by anonymous users of an e-commerce site. A dataset of interaction patterns from 592 volunteers, encompassing tasks such as *Point & Click*, *Drag & Drop*, *Text Selection*, *Text Editing*, and *Menu Item Selection*, was collected and analyzed. Various artificial intelligence (AI) models were trained to identify predictive correlations between task execution times and user demographics. Rigorous evaluation using metrics like Area Under the Curve of the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PR) demonstrated the models' efficacy in automatic user profiling, revealing the potential for highly accurate gender determination and age group estimation. These findings highlight the significant potential of AI to create systems for automatically inferring user demographics from initial interactions, enabling dynamic and personalized e-commerce experiences that enhance customer perception and potentially increase revenue.

Subjects Human-Computer Interaction, Artificial Intelligence, Data Mining and Machine Learning, Data Science

Keywords Demographic prediction, E-commerce, User interaction patterns, Age classification, Gender classification, Behavioral biometrics, Human-computer interaction (HCI)

Submitted 28 July 2025

Accepted 12 December 2025

Published 28 January 2026

Corresponding author

Martin Gonzalez-Rodriguez,
martin@uniovi.es

Academic editor

Siddhartha Bhattacharyya

Additional Information and
Declarations can be found on
page 24

DOI [10.7717/peerj-cs.3563](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.3563)

© Copyright

2026 De Andrés et al.

Distributed under

Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0

OPEN ACCESS

INTRODUCTION

The fundamental motivation of this research is driven by the commercial need for real-time personalization in e-commerce, specifically addressing the 'cold-start' problem for anonymous users. Accurate demographic prediction at the very first point of interaction is crucial for immediate content adaptation, maximizing user engagement, and boosting sales conversions. This study is motivated by the potential to transform general e-commerce experiences into highly personalized ones using only the subtle, non-intrusive timing metrics of basic user interactions, which are inherently available on any web platform.

The core objective of this study is twofold: first, to empirically determine the strength of correlation between fundamental human-computer interaction (HCI) task execution times (e.g., *Point & Click*, *Drag & Drop*, etc.) and the user's gender and age group (≤ 40 and > 40 years). Second, using this evidence, the main goal is to develop and validate a robust set of machine learning-based classification models capable of accurately predicting these

demographics for anonymous e-commerce users solely based on their initial interaction times.

User profiles (also known as user models) are essential to obtain knowledge about users of software applications in areas like e-commerce, recommendation systems, or knowledge management systems (*Schiaffino & Amandi, 2009*). This knowledge is required to improve the design quality of such applications, thus improving usability and accessibility. It plays a crucial role in information delivery by establishing effective communication between the system and the users (*Cyr et al., 2018*).

The quality of the obtained design influences the individual's perceptions and user behavior (*Floh & Madlberger, 2013*). Thus, the accuracy of these user profiles may be a determining factor in the success of online information systems (*Sebora, Lee & Sukasame, 2009; Turban et al., 2002*).

User profiles are often created and updated automatically. They are based on the observation of the user behavior along interaction sessions with the system (*Pazzani & Billsus, 2007*). In this respect, early identification of behavior patterns among users in interactive systems is crucial to create compelling user profiles (*Kambil, Eselius & Monteiro, 2000*), thus providing adaptive and customized content to meet the interaction requirements and needs of the users.

Empirical evidence shows that the different behavior patterns shown by the users of online systems may be caused by differences in their age, gender, household income, belonging to different social classes, and other factors (*Haque, Sadeghzadeh & Khatibi, 2006; Lee, 2009; Pariente-Martinez et al., 2016; De Andrés et al., 2015*).

Among these factors, age and gender are those that have shown the most significant influence on user interaction with information systems. Some authors point out that differences in age and gender are strongly related to different interaction behaviors (*Xu, Zou & Wang, 2006*). Moreover, the influence of these differences over how users interact with online systems has been reported in different scenarios (*Weiser, 2000; Freudenthal, 2001*).

However, the literature lacks strong evidence on whether behavior differences related to gender and age are strong enough to support the construction of automatic user profiling. This work intends to fill this gap, measuring the differences in the execution times recorded for users of different ages and genders when they execute some of the most popular interactive tasks found in online systems. Using such data, we constructed a series of machine learning-based classifier systems aimed at the automatic detection of the user's gender and age.

The study supporting this research measured the time required by a sample of 592 individuals to complete a series of tasks based on the execution of (i) *Point & Click*, (ii) *Drag & Drop*, (iii) *Text Selection*, (iv) *Text Edit* and (v) *Menu Item Selection* tasks. The execution time was collected automatically using data-gathering software agents.

The data obtained was used to evaluate the classification accuracy of several families of machine learning algorithms. The evaluation included Bagging, Random Forest, AdaBoost.M1, LogitBoost, Support Vector Machine (SVM) (Weka Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO)), C4.5 (J48), Logistic Regression, and Stacking. All the algorithms

were executed using 10-fold cross-validation. The results were evaluated using the Area Under the Curve of the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PR) metric, among other metrics.

Results proved that it is possible to determine the gender and to estimate the age group (over and under 40 years old) with a high level of accuracy.

As a practical application of our research results, we can highlight that the same agents used to collect data during the test are suitable to be embedded in e-commerce websites to observe the user behavior of anonymous users when they perform the same tasks (*Point & Click, Drag & Drop, etc.*) during the first seconds after arriving at the site. Then, the machine learning models tested in this research could be used to classify the users by age and gender. The user interface of such sites, as well as the information displayed, can be dynamically and automatically adapted to the users' needs.

In summary, this study proposes a novel, lightweight method for inferring age and gender solely from a minimal sequence of low-level user interface (UI) interactions—specifically *Point & Click, Drag & Drop, Text Selection, Text Typing, and Menu Item Selection*—without requiring textual input, hardware sensors, or historical data. Our work makes three key contributions: (1) we empirically establish the correlation between interaction timings and demographic attributes; (2) we develop and validate a set of machine learning classifiers that operate in real time using only these timing features; and (3) we demonstrate that accurate demographic inference is feasible within the first few seconds of user interaction, enabling immediate personalization in e-commerce cold-start scenarios.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Following the introduction, 'Background' gives a background introduction on age and gender differences concerning the interaction with computer systems. 'Methods' explains the empirical study that was conducted to gather the data needed in this research, the tested machine learning algorithms, and the validation methodology used to measure their performance. In 'Results', the obtained results are shown. Finally, 'Summary and Conclusion' includes a summary of the conclusions, and 'Limitations and Future Work' discusses the future work and the limitations of this research.

BACKGROUND

Literature shows several studies attempting to predict the age and gender of users based on their interactions and inputs in the user interface. Portions of the next descriptive text were previously published as part of the preprint of this PhD Thesis ([Pariante Martínez, 2020](#)). The analysis of the text introduced by the users in web-based forums ([Park & Woo, 2019](#)) and on social networks ([Yang et al., 2021](#); [Hosseini & Tammimy, 2016](#)) was used for this purpose. The analysis is based on counting the number of specific words employed in the texts (verbs, pronouns, articles, adjectives, adverbs, *etc.*), providing levels of accuracy when predicting the gender close to 66.66%. This textual paradigm remains dominant in demographic inference from online platforms. A recent scoping review of 74 studies by [O'Connor et al. \(2024\)](#) confirms that gender prediction from Twitter data consistently outperforms age estimation, but both rely heavily on linguistic content and substantial user histories. Complementing this, [Gomez et al. \(2024\)](#) demonstrated that

reconstructive classification using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) on social network text can effectively identify age and gender—yet still presupposes the availability of written content.

Authors like *Tsimperidis, Yucel & Katos (2021)* analyzed the keystroke (for example, the time intervals that the keys remain pressed) dynamics to a similar extent to infer age and gender. Beyond text and typing, alternative biometric and behavioral modalities have recently gained traction. For example, *Ghrban & El Abbadi (2023)* provide a comprehensive review of deep learning approaches that estimate age and gender from facial images, achieving high accuracy but requiring camera input. Similarly, handwriting analysis has emerged as a promising modality, with *Alaei & Alaei (2023)* surveying machine learning methods that infer demographics from static or dynamic handwriting features. In immersive settings, *Gil-López et al. (2023)* showed that behavioral responses in virtual reality—such as eye-tracking, body posture, and spatial navigation—can predict shopper demographics with over 70% accuracy. Even gait patterns captured *via* inertial sensors have been used to estimate user demographics in mobile contexts (*Swami, 2024*).

Other authors, however, attempted to predict the age and gender of the user through an inspection of the actions applied to the conceptual and semantic levels of the user interface. Some authors use machine learning to track the context window-based history of the user sessions (*Khan, Sohrab & Yousuf, 2020*). *Lu et al. (2015)* goes further, employing the users' web access history or the product viewing logs to infer their gender.

All these systems require a long time to gather the data required to make the prediction. In all of them, the user needs to interact for a long time and during several different sessions to build and leave a solid track of their preferences in the shopping cart, search bar, navigation story, *etc.*

Critically, the most effective recent approaches depend on either (1) user-generated text, (2) specialized hardware (*e.g.*, virtual reality headsets, inertial sensors, cameras), or (3) extended behavioral histories. None operate in the minimal, low-friction context of a standard graphical user interface with only a handful of basic interactions. There is no way to use these prototypes to provide a quick and reliable prediction just after a user performs a few interactions. To the best of our knowledge—supported by the comprehensive reviews of *O'Connor et al. (2024)*, *Ghrban & El Abbadi (2023)*, and *Alaei & Alaei (2023)*, as well as the experimental studies of *Gil-López et al. (2023)*, *Gomez et al. (2024)*, and *Swami (2024)*—no existing system infers age and gender solely from a minimal sequence of standard, low-level user interface interactions (such as *Point & Click* or *Drag & Drop*) in a conventional desktop or mobile environment, without requiring sensors, cameras, textual input, or historical data. This gap defines the novelty and practical contribution of our approach.

As summarized in [Table 1](#), existing approaches for age and gender prediction rely heavily on textual input, specialized hardware, or long interaction histories. These requirements limit their applicability during the initial phases of user interaction, highlighting the need for lightweight, real-time inference methods such as the one proposed in this work.

Table 1 Comparison of existing demographic prediction approaches. The table categorizes methods by input modality, data requirements, hardware dependencies, and limitations. It highlights the gap our work addresses: a sensor-free, text-free, real-time method based solely on low-level user interface interaction timings, enabling immediate inference during user onboarding.

Study	Input modality	Requirements	Key limitations
<i>Park & Woo (2019), Yang et al. (2021)</i>	Social media text (lexical)	Large history of user posts; standard web browser	Requires textual content; ineffective for non-writing users
<i>O'Connor et al. (2024) (review)</i>	Twitter text	Substantial tweet history; standard web	Age prediction lags significantly behind gender
<i>Gomez et al. (2024)</i>	Social network text + SVD	Multiple messages or profile text; standard web	Still depends entirely on written content
<i>Tsimperidis, Yucel & Katos (2021)</i>	Keystroke dynamics	Minutes of continuous typing; keyboard	Not applicable during brief or non-typing interactions
<i>Ghrban & El Abbadi (2023) (review)</i>	Facial images	Clear photo(s); camera required	Privacy-sensitive; fails without visual input
<i>Alaei & Alaei (2023) (review)</i>	Handwriting	Handwritten sample; digitizer or scanner	Irrelevant in typical graphic user interface interactions
<i>Gil-López et al. (2023)</i>	Virtual reality behavior (gaze, posture)	Several minutes in virtual reality; headset + trackers	Requires immersive setup; low ecological validity
<i>Swami (2024)</i>	Gait (inertial sensors)	Walking sequences; smartphone/wearable inertial measurement units	Limited to mobile contexts with motion sensors
<i>Khan, Sohrab & Yousuf (2020), Lu et al. (2015)</i>	Web logs, product views	Multiple sessions; cookies/tracking	Not real-time; fails in cold-start scenarios
Our approach	Low-level UI actions (e.g., <i>Point & Click, Drag & Drop</i>)	3–5 interactions; standard desktop/mobile (no sensors, no camera)	Enables immediate, privacy-preserving demographic inference during onboarding

Gender interaction differences

Literature shows that women and men do not differ in goal achievement when executing computer tasks, but they show strong differences in other areas, for example, in the perception of their technological capabilities (*Sobieraj & Krämer, 2020*) or their computer self-efficacy (*Christoph et al., 2015*).

Concerning interaction at the highest layers of user interfaces (conceptual and semantic levels), there is evidence that both genders process information in different ways (*Beckwith et al., 2006*). As an example, *Czerwinski, Tan & Robertson (2002)* points out that Navigation tasks are done at different levels of performance depending on gender. It was found that men's performance is better when the navigation is done in small displays, while *Tan, Czerwinski & Robertson (2003)* shows that this performance difference diminishes when using larger displays.

At this high level of interaction, there are also gender-related differences in collaborative work (*Collazos et al., 2014*), problem-solving (*Beckwith, 2003*), and decision-making (*Beckwith & Burnett, 2004*) in computer-mediated interaction.

Gender-related differences were also detected at a lower level of interaction, mainly related to the syntactic and lexical levels of user interfaces. These differences affect the way, accuracy, and speed at which certain tasks are done. It was found that when using the mouse, men require a smaller physical area than women. However, women show a greater

range of motion at the wrist (*Wahlström et al., 2000*). *Rohr (2006)* points out that men perform interaction tasks faster, but women do them with more accuracy. This observation is consistent with other studies showing that men perform faster than women in *Point & Click*, *Drag & Drop*, and *Menu Item selection* tasks (*De Andrés et al., 2015*). Another study comparing the error rate in the execution of *Point & Click* and *Drag & Drop* tasks in children revealed that girls performed worse in the second kind of tasks (*Inkpen, 2001*).

Age interaction differences

There have been several attempts to classify users by age, analyzing their interaction in the highest layers of the user interfaces (conceptual and semantic layers). In parallel work, *Nguyen et al. (2013)* proposed an automatic age prediction system from tweets, while *Dichiu & Rancea (2016)* used a similar approach to predict not only the age but the gender too.

Other studies worked at these levels to analyze the differences in the way users of different ages operate in computing environments. Several authors reported that, as the high-level cognitive skills decline with age, working in such environments becomes harder for these users (*Morrell, 2001; Xie, 2003*). This effect has been identified in tasks like information retrieval (*Freudenthal, 2001; Nap, De Greef & Bouwhuis, 2005*) or navigation (*Sayers, 2004; Neerincx et al., 2000*). These authors identified a correlation between performance and age, reporting slower execution times for older users. This finding is consistent with studies focused on the effect of age on web navigation (*Hill et al., 2011*) as well as on exploring information systems (*Tullis, 2007; Hill et al., 2011*).

A similar decline has been reported by other researchers when older users interact with the lowest layers of user interfaces, often related to the syntactic and lexical levels (*Fisk et al., 2005; Hill et al., 2011; Vines et al., 2015*). The progressive loss of muscle strength makes the motor movements required to interact with pointing devices more difficult to execute (*Walker, Philbin & Fisk, 1997; Stubbs, Fernandez & Glenn, 1993*). Aging may also produce sensory loss that may negatively affect the perception (*Dickinson, Arnott & Prior, 2007*). This hurts performance, increasing the completion times for basic interaction tasks (*Fisk et al., 2005; Hill et al., 2011*).

However, very young users show large reaction times too, even for crucial interaction tasks. *Kuhtz-Buschbeck et al. (1998)* showed that children younger than 12 years old show poor performance (compared with adults) when executing relatively complex tasks such as *Drag & Drop*). As we will explain later, this task requires coordination between the motor and the perceptive systems to keep track of the trajectory of an object, requiring multiple corrections along the path. Therefore, executing this task correctly requires both the motor and perceptive systems to work as a unique entity in perfect coordination, demanding high skills for both (*Chadwick-Dias, McNulty & Tullis, 2002; Czaja & Lee, 2007*). For authors like *Agudo, Sánchez & Rico (2010)*, the required coordination between the hand and the eye is still under development in the kids' cognitive system, hence the slow execution times.

Several researchers showed that the age of the users affects the performance in different interaction tasks (*Carvalho et al., 2015*). To some extent, the younger the users, the faster and more accurate their motor systems are *Fernandez-Lanvin et al. (2018)*,

Pariante-Martinez et al. (2016). A previous study (*De Andrés et al., 2015*) showed that the time required to complete *Point & Click* tasks notably increased among people over 40 years old. At this age, the loss of muscle strength that supports the motor system starts (*Metter et al., 1997*). Therefore, we use this minimum in the execution time function as the threshold to categorize the group of users: over and under 40 years old.

METHODS

Design of the test

An online experimental platform was developed, containing five tests that volunteers participating in the experiment had to execute. The tests were organized into five sections. Each one was targeted to measure the user skills in a different interaction task commonly found in online environments. Thereby, the interaction tasks under study were:

1. *Point & Click*. Commonly used to place the mouse pointer over a region or area to select or activate it, by clicking on it. Users of commercial sites like Amazon, Aliexpress, eBay, etc. are required to execute this task to activate the Call to Action (CTA) elements commonly found on such pages, like for example the Buy buttons.
2. *Drag & Drop*. Used to select an object and drag it over a wider area to trigger an action. The use of this interaction task is commonly required to initiate data transfer operations when the user needs to move objects from the computer to cloud storage sites, like, for example, Dropbox, Onedrive, or Google Drive. This task is also needed to interact with image-based social sites like Flickr or 500 px.
3. *Text Selection*. Used to select the fragment of text the user wants to modify with a later action. This task is frequently required to complement forms used in e-commerce applications.
4. *Text Typing*. Key-pressing actions leading to writing words. In combination with text selection, it represents a crucial interaction task required for the fulfillment of web forms.
5. *Menu Item selection*. It is a crucial task required to operate in e-commerce applications to choose an object in a menu or combo box. The execution of a prior *Point & Click* action is frequently required to activate the menu before selecting the item.

Each one of the five tests was designed to emulate the lexical and syntactical levels of the equivalent widgets embedded in an e-commerce web system. That is, the elements related to the perception system (object recognition) and motor system (typing, clicking, etc.) were the same as in the real system counterpart. However, the upper levels of the user interface (conceptual and semantic), including iconic layouts, were not implemented to avoid individuals using their previous knowledge related to real systems when using the tests. In any case, each test was coded as an independent widget, so they can easily be deployed in any e-commerce production platform.

The developed testing platform contained data-gathering agents that observed the actions done by the volunteers, recording their actions. The study strictly adhered to the principles of informed consent and data minimization. Explicit informed consent was

obtained from all volunteers prior to the collection of any data. The consent process clearly communicated the study's objective: the analysis of interaction logs to infer demographic attributes (age and gender). Participants were fully informed that their participation was voluntary, they retained the right to withdraw at any time, and their interaction patterns would be collected and subsequently processed for research purposes.

Data management prioritized participant privacy, particularly considering that demographic inference increases the risk of re-identification. The captured interaction data were fully anonymized at the point of collection. No direct Personally Identifiable Information—such as names, surnames, or email addresses—was ever recorded or linked to the interaction logs. Instead, each session was exclusively tied to a unique, non-identifiable session number. This unique identifier was generated solely for the purpose of linking the self-declared demographic data (age/gender) with the technical interaction logs. This design ensures that the data analyzed are strictly limited to technical interaction patterns and are not personally traceable, significantly mitigating the privacy risks associated with identifying individuals from their inferred demographic profiles.

The design of the test was based on the so-called **Goals, Operators, Methods, and Selection rules (GOMS)** model (*Card, Moran & Newell, 1983*). Portions of the next descriptive text were previously published as part of the preprint of this PhD Thesis (*Pariente Martínez, 2020*). The GOMS model and its multiple variations like Cognitive Perceptual Motor GOMS (CPM GOMS) (*John et al., 2002*), Sociotechnical GOMS (SGOMS) (*West & Pronovost, 2009*), etc., are models widely employed by usability specialists from diverse fields who use them to learn about human behavior (*Oyewole & Haight, 2011; Schrepp, 2010*), ranging from industrial systems (*Gong & Kieras, 1994*) to technical environments (*West & Macdougall, 2014*).

To provide accurate predictions, GOMS requires the user to perfectly know the system under study. Therefore, the volunteers need to be familiar with the execution of the five selected tasks. Individuals were recruited through the promotion of the experiment in online communities like Twitter, Facebook, and *Foro Coches* (<http://www.forocoches.com>), the most popular online community in Spain. This approach was used to select people who are used to working in online environments, so they are familiar with the knowledge and skills required to execute such tasks.

GOMS is based on a reduced set of interaction blocks called operators, which are combined to achieve complex interaction tasks. Some of the most common operators used by GOMS and its variations are P (Pointing), D (Drag), M (Mental operation, taking a decision), and K (Keying). All of them have an associated (estimated) execution time denoted as T. Therefore T_P is the time required to move the mouse to a certain position in the interface, T_D is the time required to drag an element from place to place, T_M the time required to choose a menu item and T_K is the time required to press a key in the keyboard or a key in the mouse. Therefore, the time predicted by GOMS to accomplish a complex task will be the sum of the time required by all the operators implied in its execution. The software agents embedded in the user interface of the test platform captured the execution times (T) for each operator in each user session.

Figure 1 The fundamental *Point & Click Task* (analyzed using the GOMS model) begins with the user executing a Pointing (*P*) operator to start moving the mouse toward the target (Step A), involving continuous fine trajectory corrections during the pointer movement (Step B), and concludes when the user performs a Keying (*K*) operator by clicking on the target to select it (Step C); consequently, the total execution time (*T*) predicted by GOMS for this task is the sum of these two primary operators: $T = T_P + T_K$. [Full-size !\[\]\(43e4e85f3e07c993849f98a1fa87e486_img.jpg\) DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-1](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-1)

The *Point & Click* test (test 1) displayed a series of rectangles resembling CTAs that the user had to click on. Each CTA object appeared at a different location each time, reducing its size during the sequence. [Figure 1](#) illustrates the design of this test.

The time required to execute each *P* operator in the test (T_P), that is, the time required to move the pointer over the CTA is predicted by Fitts's law ([Zhai, 2004](#)). This scientific law estimates this time as a function of the ratio between the distance to the target and its width, multiplied by a correction factor than depends on each user's performance ([Guiard, Olafsdottir & Perrault, 2011](#)). Therefore, this factor may be related to the variables under analysis in this work (age and gender). Placing the pointer on the right location requires several corrections when aiming for the target, modifying the trajectory to increase the accuracy ([Phillips & Triggs, 2001](#)). Changes in location and size for the target at each iteration of the test were used to increase the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) along the measurements.

The design of the *Drag & Drop* test (test 2) is illustrated in [Fig. 2](#). During this second test, the volunteers had to drag a small rectangle over a larger one several times. Due to the same reason described for test 1 and also related to Fitt's law, the size and location of both rectangles changed regularly at each iteration.

The *Text Selection* test (test 3) combines *Point & Click* tasks and drag operators to select a proposed word. For the same reason described in the previous tests, this process was repeated several times during the test, changing the location and size of the candidate word at each interaction. [Figure 3](#) describes the design of this test.

Figure 2 The *Drag & Drop* Task (analyzed using the GOMS model) is a sequence of three primary operations: the task begins in Step A with the user performing a Keying (*K*) operation by clicking on the object, immediately followed by initiating the drag motion toward the target using the Drawing/ Dragging (*D*) operator; Step B represents the period of sustained *D* operation where the user makes continuous positional corrections during the object's trajectory; and finally, in Step C, the task concludes with another Keying (*K*) operator when the user releases the mouse button to drop the item, yielding a total GOMS predicted execution time of $T = T_K + T_D + T_K$.

Full-size DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-2

Figure 3 The *Text Selection* Task (analyzed using the GOMS model) consists of a sequence of four operators: first, the user performs a Pointing (*P*) operation by moving the mouse to the starting point of the text to be selected (Step A); next, they initiate the selection with a Keying (*K*) operation by pressing the mouse button (Step B); this is immediately followed by a Dragging (*D*) operation as the user moves the pointer to the end of the desired text range; finally, the user completes the selection in Step C by releasing the mouse button, which constitutes the final Keying (*K*) operation. The total execution time (T) predicted by the GOMS model for this sequence is the sum of these times: $T = T_P + T_K + T_D + T_K$.

Full-size DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-3

Figure 4 The Text Typing Task (analyzed using GOMS) involves the user starting to input text by pressing the initial key, often the Enter or Intro key, and then continuing with the subsequent characters; since the primary operator in this scenario is Keying (K), the execution time (T) predicted by the GOMS model for the entire task is calculated as the time taken for a single K operation (T_K) multiplied by the total number of keys pressed during the typing sequence: $T = T_K \times (\text{number of keys pressed})$. [Full-size !\[\]\(e4c51d9db35ee9651ed60d72acdb782c_img.jpg\) DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-4](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-4)

Figure 4 describes the design of the *Text Typing* test (test 4). Salthouse's regularities predict the time required by different kinds of users to type texts of a given size, which can be measured using the number of keying operators required for its completion (K) (Salthouse, 1984).

Test 5 measures the time required to complete the *Menu Item selection* task. While Fitt's law estimates the time to click on the menu name, and once it is deployed, the time to click on the desired item, the time a single user needs to decide what item of the menu should be chosen is estimated by another scientific law. The Hicks–Hymans law estimates the time required to make a decision (T_M) as a linear increase related to the logarithm of the number of alternatives the user has to evaluate, as well as some user-performance-dependent correction factors (Rosati, 2013; Schneider & Anderson, 2011). Again, these correction factors may be related to the variables under analysis. At each iteration, the location and size (number of available options) changed for the reason described above. The design of this test is described in **Fig. 5**.

Selection of machine learning algorithms

The selection of machine learning algorithms for this study—including Bagging, Random Forest, AdaBoost.M1, LogitBoost, SVM (Weka SMO), C4.5 (J48), Logistic Regression, and Stacking—is driven by a strategy focused on robustness and comprehensive evaluation for a binary classification problem. The core methodological challenge is the classification of demographics (gender and binary age) using sparse and potentially noisy timing metrics derived from initial user interactions, a scenario characterized by high variability.

Figure 5 The Menu Item Selection Task (analyzed using GOMS) involves a sequence of four fundamental operators: first, the user performs a Pointing (*P*) operation by moving the mouse to the menu title (Step A); second, they execute a Keying (*K*) operation by clicking the mouse to deploy the menu (Step B); third, a second Pointing (*P*) operation is performed as the user moves the pointer to the desired item (Step C); and finally, the task is completed with a second Keying (*K*) operation—clicking the mouse button to select the item, with the total execution time predicted by GOMS being the sum of these operators: $T = T_P + T_K + T_P + T_K$.

Full-size DOI: 10.7717/peerj-cs.3563/fig-5

To ensure stability and generalizability in the presence of noisy, real-world data, ensemble methods were prioritized. Algorithms such as Random Forest and Bagging are crucial for reducing the high variance typically associated with single tree-based models (like C4.5/J48), leading to more reliable predictions. Conversely, boosting methods (AdaBoost.M1, and LogitBoost) were included to effectively reduce bias, iteratively improving performance by focusing computational effort on misclassified instances.

The selection also incorporated models from diverse algorithmic families to ensure a fair and exhaustive comparison across different approaches. Logistic Regression serves as an essential linear baseline model, allowing the performance gains of more complex non-linear techniques to be accurately measured. The Support Vector Machine (SVM), utilizing the kernel method, was included to test the efficacy of kernel-based methods in separating classes within the high-dimensional feature space generated by the time-based interaction metrics.

Finally, the Stacking meta-learning technique was integrated to assess whether a hierarchical combination of the various base models could yield superior predictive accuracy than any single algorithm. By leveraging the complementary strengths of the diverse classifiers, Stacking is intended to optimize the final classification outcome, which is crucial for achieving the “high level of accuracy” required for practical demographic prediction in the critical e-commerce cold-start phase.

Selection of performance metrics

Receiver Operator Characteristic analysis (ROC) is commonly used to present results for binary decision problems in machine learning (Ling, Huang & Zhang, 2003; Hernández-Orallo, Flach & Ferri, 2012). The result of ROC analysis is a performance measure called Area Under Curve (AUC) (Ling & Li, 1998). This is the recommended metric score for the classifiers by Provost, Fawcett & Kohavi (1998). However, when dealing with highly skewed data sets, Precision-Recall (PR) curves give a more informative picture of an algorithm's performance (Davis & Goadrich, 2006). The metric that measures the performance of this curve is called Area Under Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PR) (Davis & Goadrich, 2006; Liu & Chawla, 2011).

Prior literature suggested that due to the information loss assumption may be more suitable for highly imbalanced data sets (Tang et al., 2008; Khan & Rana, 2019). In this regard, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is another suitable well known metric (Becerra-Fernandez, Zanakis & Walczak, 2002; Çakır, Çalış & Küçükşille, 2009).

Working with unbalanced data sets is one of the biggest challenges in data mining (Japkowicz & Stephen, 2002; Chawla, Japkowicz & Kotcz, 2004). The class imbalance problem arises when the class of interest is relatively rare as compared with other classes. In this case, we will assume that the positive class (or class of interest) is the minority class, and the negative class is the majority class. The data set used in this study contains unbalanced data, as we will show in the following sections. The minority classes are represented by individuals above 40 years old (in the case of age) or females (in the case of gender). Both classes were considered positive classes, and because of that, were labeled as 1. On the contrary, males and individuals under 40 years old are more common and were considered as class label 0 or negative classes. As indicated above, Boosting-based algorithms were used for handling class imbalance (Chawla et al., 2003; Domingos, 1999).

To assess the performance in this study, we report a list of selected metrics, mostly based on current practices in the field (AUC, AUC-PR, F-score, RMSE, True Positive Rate (TPR or recall), and True Negative Rate (TNR or specificity). Despite reporting six performance measures, the final ordering was generated by AUC-PR. As indicated above, it is the most widely accepted regarding our unbalanced case (Tang et al., 2008; Khan & Rana, 2019).

Validation strategy

To assess the predictive performance of each algorithm, we run k-fold cross-validation multiple times. To get the final prediction performance for the model the average is calculated. Within the test, to obtain reliable performances, we repeated 10 times a 10-fold cross-validation procedure.

After obtaining those metrics, we compared the performance of each model against the others in order to be able to know which one fits better with our data set. This analysis will allow us, on the one hand to determine whether it would be possible to build a reliable classifier system and on the other hand, to determine what would be the best machine-learning algorithm to be used in this context. For this purpose, we used the paired two-sample t-test comparing the means of the AUC-PR of the different models considered

Table 2 Frequency distribution.

	Male	Female	Total
Under 40	411	117	528
Over 40	51	13	64
Total	462	130	592

two by two. This test is carried out at the 0.05 level of significance. In addition, we calculate a confidence interval of 95% for the mean value.

Hyperparameter configuration

All machine learning algorithms were implemented using the Weka 3.9 framework with default hyperparameters unless otherwise specified. Specifically:

- **Random Forest:** a total of 100 trees, maximum depth unlimited, and number of features per split set to \sqrt{p} (where p is the number of input features).
- **Bagging:** a total of 100 iterations of J48 as base classifier, with resampling enabled.
- **AdaBoost.M1** and **LogitBoost:** a total of 100 iterations with decision stumps as weak learners.
- **SMO (SVM):** used the PolyKernel with exponent = 1 and $C = 1.0$; no cost-sensitive adjustments were applied.
- **Logistic Regression:** no ridge penalty (*i.e.*, $\lambda = 0$).
- **J48:** confidence factor = 0.25, minimum number of instances per leaf = 2.
- **Stacking:** used LogitBoost as meta-classifier and the remaining classifiers as base learners.

These configurations reflect common default settings in the literature for comparative benchmarking and were kept consistent across all experiments to ensure fairness in performance evaluation.

Cross-validation strategy and stratification

The 10-fold cross-validation procedure was repeated 10 times (yielding 100 folds in total) to reduce variance in performance estimates. Each outer fold was stratified with respect to the target variable (*i.e.*, gender or age group) to preserve the original class distribution in both training and test partitions. This ensured that minority classes (females for gender; users over 40 for age) were adequately represented in every fold, which is critical given the class imbalance reported in [Table 2](#).

Handling of missing and noisy data

The data-collection agents recorded execution times for all five interaction tasks with millisecond precision. No missing values were observed in the raw dataset, as the experimental platform required the completion of all tasks before submission. To address potential outliers or noisy measurements (*e.g.*, due to temporary system lag or user distraction), we applied the Interquartile Range (IQR) rule per task: any execution time

falling below $Q1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR$ or above $Q3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ was winsorized to the nearest fence value rather than removed, preserving sample size while mitigating extreme influence. Less than 1.2% of observations were affected by this procedure.

Feature preprocessing

Prior to model training, all execution-time features were standardized using z-score normalization (zero mean and unit variance) to ensure comparability across tasks with different time scales (e.g., Point&Click vs. Text Editing). No explicit feature selection was performed; all five interaction times (one per task) were used as input features for every model. This decision was motivated by the small feature space and the interpretability goal of assessing the contribution of each basic interaction task to demographic prediction.

Participant recruitment and sampling strategy

Participants were recruited through voluntary participation *via* public online channels, including Twitter (now X), Facebook, and ForoCoches (the largest Spanish-language online forum). This convenience sampling strategy aimed to gather a diverse pool of users familiar with standard web interactions, ensuring ecological validity for e-commerce contexts. No monetary incentives were provided. To be included in the dataset, participants were required to: (1) complete all five interaction tasks without interruption, and (2) provide self-reported demographic information (age and gender) *via* a brief questionnaire before testing. No stratification by age or gender was applied during recruitment; however, the resulting sample ($N = 592$) naturally reflected moderate class imbalance (see Table 2), which our modeling strategy explicitly addressed through the use of robust evaluation metrics (AUC-PR).

Data filtering and quality control

Before model training, the raw interaction logs underwent a two-stage filtering process. First, sessions with missing or null execution times were discarded—though none were found, as the platform enforced task completion. Second, we applied a behavioral plausibility check: any task execution time shorter than 500 ms (physiologically implausible for complex motor-cognitive tasks) or longer than the 99.5th percentile of its task distribution was flagged. Rather than discarding these cases, we applied winsorization (as detailed in ‘Handling of Missing and Noisy Data’) to limit undue influence while preserving statistical power. In total, fewer than 1.5% of task-level observations were adjusted. No participant was excluded based on performance outliers alone, to avoid biasing the sample toward “typical” users and to maintain the realism of deployment scenarios with heterogeneous user behavior.

Model deployment and real-time operation

The trained models are designed for lightweight real-time deployment on e-commerce frontends. The data-gathering agents record execution times for the five canonical tasks during the user’s first seconds on the site. These five timing values are standardized using the same z-score parameters (mean and standard deviation) derived from the training data and then fed into the selected classifier. The entire inference pipeline—feature extraction,

Table 3 Descriptive statistics for the independent variables in the study (execution times are measured in milliseconds).

	Mean	Std. dev.	Min.	Max.
<i>Point & Click</i>	16,870.3970	4,292.5680	9,319	45,792
<i>Drag & Drop</i>	32,858.7872	10,620.8291	19,595	159,867
<i>Text selection</i>	59,382.8260	29,775.9585	16,780	534,397
<i>Text edit</i>	83,985.5980	53,980.0728	13,689	635,472
<i>Menu selection</i>	61,155.9392	14,075.6995	38,351	147,630

normalization, and prediction—can be executed client-side or server-side with minimal latency.

RESULTS

Descriptive analysis

The number of participants in the experiment was 592. They were categorized according to their age and gender. This information was provided by the users through a questionnaire filled out just before the tests started. The demographics of the participants related to their age and gender are included in [Table 2](#). Based on previous research ([Pariente-Martinez et al., 2016](#)), it was found that age and gender influenced the performance while executing interaction tasks. Because of that, we used the time consumed by those users while performing each of the tests explained in ‘Design of the Test’, measured in milliseconds, as features for our machine learning models. In addition, it has been proved that older people perform worse than young people ([De Andrés et al., 2015](#)) and there is an age threshold set at 40 where the performance starts to decrease ([De Andrés et al., 2015](#)). Therefore, to allow us to classify the users based on their age, we split the data based on their age into two groups: under and over 40 years old. Regarding gender classification, the data is split based on the user’s gender (male, female). The frequency distributions are shown in [Table 2](#).

Concerning the execution times of the different tasks, the descriptive statistics are shown in [Table 3](#). As we might expect, the average execution time depends on the complexity of the test. As mentioned previously, some authors [MacKenzie, Sellen & Buxton \(1991\)](#), [Chadwick-Dias, McNulty & Tullis \(2002\)](#), [Czaja & Lee \(2007\)](#) reported a higher level of complexity in the execution of *Drag & Drop* tasks when compared with *Point & Click*. Notice that while the *Point & Click* and the *Drag & Drop* tasks required the execution of single P or D operators, the *Item Selection* task requires the execution of two P operators (one for menu activation and another one for item selection). Besides that, *Text Selection*, *Text Edit*, and *Menu Selection* require the execution of a complex M operator to decide what item to select or key to press in case of the *Text Edit* task.

Age classification analysis

After executing a 10 repeated 10-fold cross-validation with each of the models, the tested models produced a set of classification devices with varying performance results for each bootstrap replicate. The means of the most important metrics are shown below in [Table 4](#).

Table 4 Models metrics for age classification.

	AUC PR	AUC	F-score	RMSE	TPR	TNR
LogitBoost	0.9785	0.8705	0.9546	0.2689	0.9776	0.4190
RandomForest	0.9743	0.8620	0.9580	0.2518	0.9841	0.4186
AdaBoost	0.9728	0.8566	0.9577	0.2547	0.9848	0.4076
Bagging	0.9699	0.8203	0.9457	0.2783	0.9811	0.2290
Stacking	0.9680	0.8403	0.9544	0.2595	0.9780	0.4117
Logistic regression	0.9631	0.7891	0.9377	0.2969	0.9801	0.0910
J48	0.9183	0.6218	0.9420	0.3028	0.9771	0.1962
SMO	0.8919	0.5000	0.9429	0.3285	1	0

The results are ordered by AUC-PR. We can see that LogitBoost is the algorithm that yields the best AUC-PR mean performance.

The interval of confidence was calculated at 95% for the mean value of AUC-PR for each model, it is shown in Table 5. In this table, we can see that LogitBoost achieves high performance and its interval almost doesn't intersect with those of the closest models in terms of performance, that is, the Random Forest and AdaBoost intervals. In other words, those intervals are almost disjointed, and for that, LogitBoost has the best AUC-PR metric. On the other hand, Random Forest and Adaboost achieve a similar performance, which is higher than that of the rest of the algorithms. On the contrary, J48 and SMO achieve the worst performance, as their confidence intervals are completely disjoint from those of the rest of the models.

To determine the best-performing model, the sets of overall classification results were compared two by two using the paired two-sample t-test against the Null hypothesis (H_0) of equal means, with a significant probability of 5%. The results for this test can be seen in Table 6. It can be seen that in most cases, the Null hypothesis of equal means is rejected. Those cells are highlighted with a grey background in the table. According to the results of this table and the previous ones, the LogitBoost model mean is considered significantly similar to the Random Forest model mean, and it is superior to the rest of the algorithms. Random Forests and LogitBoost achieve similar performance, as the weak learner for LogitBoost is a Random Forests model. This is following some prior research efforts that conclude that LogitBoost reduces the training errors linearly and hence yields better generalization (Friedman, Hastie & Tibshirani, 2000).

On the other hand, the rest of the models yield lower performance. Results for J48 and SMO confirm the findings in Table 5, evidencing that these models are the worst performers. The SMO bad performance agrees with the literature regarding this algorithm being highly affected by the presence of unbalanced data (Tang et al., 2008).

Gender classification analysis

The means of the computed metrics for each algorithm in its application to the classification problem are shown in Table 7. The results are ordered by AUC-PR, as it is the metric that we selected to evaluate the performance of each model. We can see that

Table 5 Confidence interval at 95% of the mean value of AUC-PR metrics for age classification.

	AUC PR	
	Confidence interval	
LogitBoost	0.9755	0.9815
RandomForest	0.9706	0.9780
AdaBoost	0.9688	0.9767
Bagging	0.9664	0.9735
Stacking	0.9646	0.9714
Logistic regression	0.9586	0.9675
J48	0.9130	0.9236
SMO	0.8904	0.8935

Table 6 Results of paired two-sample t-test with equal means as null hypothesis for age classification.

AUC-PR	LogitB.	AdaB.	RF	J48	Stack.	SMO	Log. Reg.
1. LogitB.							
t-statistic	-						
p-value							
2. AdaB.	1 > 2						
t-statistic	-2.29	-					
p-value	0.023						
3. RF	1 = 3	2 = 3					
t-statistic	1.72	-0.57	-				
p-value	0.086	0.567					
4. J48	1 > 4	2 > 4	3 > 4				
t-statistic	19.58	16.38	-17.17	-			
p-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001				
5. Stacking	1 > 5	2 = 5	3 > 5	4 < 5			
t-statistic	4.55	1.81	-2.48	15.63	-		
p-value	<0.001	0.072	0.014	<0.001			
6. SMO	1 > 6	2 > 6	3 > 6	4 > 6	5 > 6		
t-statistic	-50.61	-37.98	-40.61	-9.48	-40.12	-	
p-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001		
7. Log. Reg.	1 > 7	2 > 7	3 > 7	4 < 7	5 = 7	6 < 7	
t-statistic	-5.7	-3.24	-3.86	12.84	-1.75	30.00	-
p-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.082	<0.001	
8. Bagging	1 > 8	2 = 8	3 = 8	4 < 8	5 = 8	6 < 8	7 < 8
t-statistic	-3.61	1.05	-1.68	16.00	0.77	-39.55	-2.39
p-value	<0.001	0.294	0.094	<0.001	0.443	<0.001	0.018

Note:

1. LogitBoost, 2. AdaBoost, 3. Random forest, 4. J48, 5. Stacking, 6. SMO, 7. Logistic, 8. Bagging. The cells where the test rejects the hypothesis of equality of means are highlighted with a grey background.

Table 7 Models metrics for gender classification.

	AUC PR	AUC	F-score	RMSE	TPR	TNR
Bagging	0.8666	0.6403	0.8672	0.4104	0.9638	0.0800
AdaBoost	0.8592	0.6312	0.8600	0.4192	0.9416	0.1200
RandomForest	0.8584	0.6307	0.8638	0.4153	0.9463	0.1308
Logistic regression	0.8522	0.6405	0.8747	0.4040	0.9805	0.0715
LogitBoost	0.8515	0.6144	0.8554	0.4648	0.9258	0.1531
Stacking	0.8236	0.5773	0.8719	0.4160	0.9832	0.0346
J48	0.7811	0.5012	0.8711	0.4179	0.9870	0.0100
SMO	0.7804	0.5000	0.8767	0.4686	1	0

Table 8 Confidence interval at 95% of the mean value of AUC-PR metrics for gender classification.

	AUC PR
	Confidence interval
Bagging	0.8584 0.8747
AdaBoost	0.8510 0.8674
RandomForest	0.8503 0.8666
Logistic regression	0.8425 0.8618
LogitBoost	0.8425 0.8605
Stacking	0.8167 0.8306
J48	0.7793 0.7828
SMO	0.7801 0.7807

Bagging is the algorithm that yielded the highest AUC-PR. In addition, if we compare these results with the results obtained for the age classification problem, it is evident that the age results are more accurate than these. As we indicated above in the literature review, there are a lot of studies that analyze the effects of age and prove that aging negatively impacts the ability to use computers (*Fisk et al., 2005; Hill et al., 2011*), thus reducing the performance when using technology (*Vines et al., 2015*). Those effects are more evident in our research than the gender differences.

As for the case of age, the confidence intervals were calculated at 95% for the mean value of AUC-PR for each model. The results are shown in [Table 8](#). In this table, we can see that the Bagging, AdaBoost and Random Forest model intervals are quite similar, although, in the Bagging interval, the upper boundary is higher than those of the other two models. On the other hand, SMO and J48 yield worse results; their intervals are quite similar and disjointed with those of the rest of the algorithms.

To determine the best-performing model, the sets of overall classification results are compared two by two using the paired two-sample t-test following the same procedure as for the age classification problem. The results for this set of tests can be seen in [Table 9](#). The cells where the test rejects the hypothesis of equality of means are highlighted with a grey background in the table. According to the results of this table and the previous ones, the Bagging model mean is considered significantly

Table 9 Results of paired two-sample t-test with equal means as null hypothesis for gender classification.

AUC-PR	LogitB.	AdaB.	RF	J48	Stack.	SMO	Log. Reg.
1. LogitB.							
t-statistic	–						
p-value							
2. AdaB.	1 = 2						
t-statistic	1.25	–					
p-value	0.212						
3. RF	1 = 3	2 = 3					
t-statistic	–1.12	–0.14	–				
p-value	0.262	0.891					
4. J48	1 > 4	2 > 4	3 > 4				
t-statistic	15.27	18.45	–18.39	–			
p-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001				
5. Stacking	1 > 5	2 > 5	3 > 5	4 < 5			
t-statistic	4.87	6.55	–6.43	11.74	–		
p-value	<0.001	0.001	0.001	<0.001			
6. SMO	1 > 6	2 > 6	3 > 6	4 = 6	5 > 6		
t-statistic	–15.71	–19.03	–18.97	–0.72	–12.29	–	
p-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.475	<0.001		
7. Log. Reg.	1 = 7	2 = 7	3 = 7	4 < 7	5 = 7	6 < 7	
t-statistic	0.09	–1.1	–0.98	14.35	4.75	4.72	–
p-value	0.925	0.272	0.329	<0.001	0.001	<0.001	
8. Bagging	1 < 8	2 = 8	3 = 8	4 < 8	5 < 8	6 < 8	7 < 8
t-statistic	2.46	–1.26	1.4	20.28	7.93	20.9	2.26
p-value	0.015	0.208	0.162	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.025

Note:

1. LogitBoost, 2. AdaBoost, 3. Random forest, 4. J48, 5. Stacking, 6. SMO, 7. Logistic, 8. Bagging. The cells where the test rejects the hypothesis of equality of means are highlighted with a grey background.

similar to the Random Forest and AdaBoost model means; thus, these models are the ones with the best performance. Bagging is also significantly better than the rest of the models.

On the contrary, SMO and J48 model means are not significantly different, but they are significantly worse than the other models. This result is similar to that obtained for the age classification problem.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates the feasibility of automatically predicting the gender and age group (over/under 40) of anonymous e-commerce website visitors by analyzing their execution times on basic interaction tasks. This is a significant finding as it addresses the gap in the literature regarding strong evidence for such automatic user profiling.

LogitBoost and Random Forests emerged as the best-performing algorithms based on the AUC-PR metric for age classification. While LogitBoost showed a slightly superior mean AUC-PR, its performance was statistically similar to Random Forests. The confidence intervals also suggest a robust performance for these two models. Conversely, SMO consistently performed poorly, likely due to the unbalanced nature of the age data (more users under 40) and its known sensitivity to such datasets ([Muntean et al., 2010](#); [Tang et al., 2008](#)).

For gender classification, Bagging, Random Forests, and AdaBoost showed the best and statistically similar performance in terms of AUC-PR. The confidence intervals for these models were also comparable. Similar to age classification, SMO and J48 yielded the worst results, again potentially linked to the data imbalance (fewer female participants) ([Tang et al., 2008](#); [Flach, 2003](#)).

It's noteworthy that the accuracy achieved for age prediction was generally higher than for gender prediction. This aligns with existing literature suggesting that age has a more pronounced impact on user interaction patterns with technology compared to gender ([Fisk et al., 2005](#); [Hill et al., 2011](#); [Vines et al., 2015](#)). The observed differences in execution times between age groups and genders in tasks like *Point & Click*, *Drag & Drop*, etc. support the ability of machine learning models to differentiate these groups.

The use of AUC-PR as the primary metric for evaluation is appropriate given the unbalanced nature of the datasets for both age and gender. This metric provides a more informative picture of the algorithms' performance in the presence of class imbalance compared to accuracy alone.

The principal strength of this work lies in establishing the high predictive feasibility of inferring key demographics (gender and binary age group) for anonymous users during the critical cold-start phase. The study's core value proposition is its non-intrusive methodology, which successfully leverages subtle Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) task execution timings instead of relying on explicit profile data or extensive transaction histories. This approach is highly scalable and practical, demonstrating a robust predictive accuracy that provides significant potential for dynamic, real-time personalization in e-commerce. While the research strongly supports its main hypothesis, two aspects warrant further expansion. First, it is recognized that the age classification remains at a binary level (≤ 40 vs. > 40). This categorization, while valuable for initial segmentation, naturally limits the granularity of personalized experiences and represents a clear avenue for future model refinement. Second, the experimental focus was exclusively on maximizing accuracy (AUC-PR). Consequently, the article did not include a dedicated analysis of the computational cost of the complex ensemble models.

While rigorous evaluation showed that ensemble methods, particularly *Random Forest* and *Stacking*, achieved the peak predictive performance (highest AUC-PR scores), the practical implications for real-world e-commerce deployment mandate a critical assessment of computational efficiency. The observed superior accuracy of these complex models comes at the expense of increased operational overhead, specifically in terms of inference latency and memory footprint. For deployment in high-traffic, real-time personalization systems, where every millisecond of delay directly impacts user experience

and conversion rates, this trade-off becomes critical. Consequently, although the final model selection based purely on accuracy favors the ensemble techniques, the most suitable model for immediate industrial application may be a simpler one, such as an optimized *Logistic Regression* or a pruned *C4.5 (J48)* tree. These lighter-weight models, despite showing marginally lower AUC-PR in our analysis, offer significantly faster execution times, which could ultimately represent the optimal balance between predictive performance and operational cost-efficiency required for low-latency, real-time demographic profiling. The detailed benchmarking of these algorithms concerning training time, inference speed, and resource consumption is therefore established as the primary focus for future work.

The high predictive capability demonstrated in this study—the inference of sensitive demographic features like age and gender from non-invasive interaction patterns—introduces significant ethical and privacy implications that must be carefully addressed. While our research used strictly anonymized and de-identified behavioral data, the ability to infer personal attributes raises concerns about potential re-identification and unwanted profiling. Any commercial deployment of this methodology must rigorously adhere to data protection regulations (*e.g.*, General Data Protection Regulation), ensuring full transparency for users regarding data collection and providing clear opt-out mechanisms.

While not the primary focus of this study, the ability to predict age and gender based on interaction patterns can serve as an additional layer of verification in online systems aimed at detecting false identities. Inconsistencies between a user's self-reported age and gender and the automatically predicted demographic profile based on their interaction behavior could raise a flag and trigger further verification processes. For example, if a user claims to be in a younger age group but their interaction patterns (slower execution times, different error rates, *etc.*) strongly suggest an older demographic, the system could prompt for additional identity confirmation. This approach could be particularly useful in scenarios where explicit identity verification is challenging or creates friction for legitimate users. By passively analyzing interaction patterns, systems can build a behavioral biometric profile that contributes to a more holistic assessment of a user's claimed identity. It is crucial to note that relying solely on age and gender prediction for fraud detection is insufficient and could lead to biases and inaccurate conclusions. However, when integrated with other security measures and identity verification techniques, it can contribute to a more robust system for identifying potentially fraudulent activities and false identities in online systems.

It is also worth noting that our preprocessing step of winsorizing outliers was applied under controlled experimental conditions to mitigate measurement noise. In a real-world e-commerce setting, interaction-level noise is likely to be more pronounced due to factors such as device heterogeneity, network latency, user multitasking, and environmental distractions. While winsorization remains a robust method for handling extreme values, future deployments should incorporate adaptive noise-filtering techniques and real-time calibration to maintain prediction accuracy under such variable conditions. This would ensure that the models remain reliable despite the increased signal variability typical of authentic browsing sessions.

In conclusion, this research provides valuable insights into the potential of using machine learning to automatically profile anonymous users based on their interaction patterns. The practical applications for e-commerce in terms of personalization are evident and promising. Furthermore, the findings suggest that such profiling, particularly when discrepancies arise between predicted and self-reported demographics, could be a useful supplementary tool in systems designed to enhance the detection of false identities online. Future work could explore the inclusion of other demographic factors and a more granular age classification to further refine the accuracy and applicability of these models.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A primary limitation of this study relates to the volunteer sample's potential homogeneity. While the dataset size ($N = 592$) is robust, the participants were recruited primarily from a local or regional context, which introduces a possible geographic and cultural bias. Furthermore, the environment for data collection was standardized, potentially limiting the variability in user interaction patterns that might arise from diverse device types (e.g., various screen sizes, operating systems) or real-world ambient conditions. Future research should aim to validate these findings using a more geographically and culturally diverse sample collected across a wider spectrum of end-user devices to confirm the external validity of our predictive models.

It is important to note that our data collection was performed under relatively controlled conditions to ensure the cleanliness and reliability of the interaction data. This approach inherently differs from the noisy, complex environment of a real e-commerce setting, where users are often multitasking, subject to distractions, or experiencing varying levels of mental fatigue. Consequently, the high accuracy metrics achieved in this study may reflect an optimized scenario. The generalizability of these results to live e-commerce platforms, where the signal-to-noise ratio is typically lower, remains an area for further investigation. Future work is needed to specifically test the models' resilience to the 'noise' and variability inherent in unconstrained, real-world browsing sessions.

A third limitation stems from the simplification of demographic categories used in this study. For the sake of a clear initial investigation, we modeled age as a binary classification (under/over 40) and utilized a binary categorization for gender. While this approach effectively demonstrated the feasibility of demographic prediction from micro-interactions, it is an oversimplification of human diversity. Age is a continuous variable, and grouping it into just two buckets disregards the more nuanced cognitive and motor changes that occur across different life stages. Similarly, a binary gender classification does not reflect the full spectrum of user identities. Future efforts should focus on developing more sophisticated models capable of multi-class age classification (e.g., 5- or 10-year brackets) or age regression, and exploring more inclusive and nuanced approaches to modeling gender.

Furthermore, the binary age classification (under/over 40 years) represents a deliberate simplification for this initial investigation. While this threshold is grounded in motor performance literature and provided a clear target for model development, it does not capture the continuous nature of aging or more nuanced age-related differences in

interaction patterns. Future studies could extend this work by employing multi-class age brackets or regression-based approaches to achieve finer-grained demographic profiling, which would be valuable for more personalized adaptive interfaces.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION AND DECLARATIONS

Funding

This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities and co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under project PID2024-155586OB-I00 (MCIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033). Additional support was provided by the Government of the Principality of Asturias through grant GRU-GIC-24-070. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Grant Disclosures

The following grant information was disclosed by the authors:

Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities.

European Regional Development Fund (ERDF): PID2024-155586OB-I00 (MCIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033).

Government of the Principality of Asturias: GRU-GIC-24-070.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author Contributions

- Javier De Andrés conceived and designed the experiments, analyzed the data, authored or reviewed drafts of the article, and approved the final draft.
- Daniel Fernandez-Lanvin conceived and designed the experiments, authored or reviewed drafts of the article, and approved the final draft.
- Martin Gonzalez-Rodriguez conceived and designed the experiments, prepared figures and/or tables, authored or reviewed drafts of the article, and approved the final draft.
- Beatriz Pariente-Martinez performed the experiments, performed the computation work, prepared figures and/or tables, authored or reviewed drafts of the article, and approved the final draft.

Data Availability

The following information was supplied regarding data availability:

The raw data and code are available in the [Supplemental Files](#).

Supplemental Information

Supplemental information for this article can be found online at <http://dx.doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.3563#supplemental-information>.

REFERENCES

- Agudo J, Sánchez H, Rico M. 2010.** Playing games on the screen: adapting mouse interaction at early ages. In: *2010 10th IEEE International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies*, 493–497 DOI [10.1109/ICALT.2010.142](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICALT.2010.142).
- Alaei F, Alaei A. 2023.** Review of age and gender detection methods based on handwriting analysis. *Neural Computing and Applications* **35**(27):24287–24310 DOI [10.1007/s00521-023-08996-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-023-08996-x).
- Becerra-Fernandez I, Zanakis S, Walczak S. 2002.** Knowledge discovery techniques for predicting country investment risk. *Computers & Industrial Engineering* **43**:787–800 DOI [10.1016/S0360-8352\(02\)00140-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-8352(02)00140-7).
- Beckwith L. 2003.** Gender HCI issues in end-user software engineering. In: *Proceedings of IEEE Symposium on Human Centric Computing Languages and Environments*, 273–274.
- Beckwith L, Burnett MG. 2004.** Gender: an important factor in end-user programming environments? In: *IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages and Human Centric Computing*, 107–114 DOI [10.1109/VLHCC.2004.28](https://doi.org/10.1109/VLHCC.2004.28).
- Beckwith L, Burnett M, Grigoreanu V, Wiedenbeck S. 2006.** Gender HCI: what about the software? *Computer* **39**(11):97–101 DOI [10.1109/mc.2006.382](https://doi.org/10.1109/mc.2006.382).
- Çakır A, Çalış H, Küçükşille EU. 2009.** Data mining approach for supply unbalance detection in induction motor. *Expert Systems with Applications* **36**(9):11808–11813 DOI [10.1016/j.eswa.2009.04.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2009.04.006).
- Card S, Moran T, Newell A. 1983.** *The psychology of human-computer interaction*. Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Carvalho D, Bessa M, Magalhaes L, Carrapatoso E. 2015.** Interaction paradigms versus age-related user profiles: an evaluation on content selection. *IEEE Latin America Transactions* **13**(2):532–539 DOI [10.1109/tla.2015.7055575](https://doi.org/10.1109/tla.2015.7055575).
- Chadwick-Dias A, McNulty M, Tullis T. 2002.** Web usability and age: how design changes can improve performance. In: *ACM SIGCAPH Computers and the Physically Handicapped*, 30–37 DOI [10.1145/960201.957212](https://doi.org/10.1145/960201.957212).
- Chawla N, Japkowicz N, Kotcz A. 2004.** Special issue on learning from imbalanced data sets. *ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter* **6**:1–6 DOI [10.1145/1007730.1007733](https://doi.org/10.1145/1007730.1007733).
- Chawla N, Lazarevic A, Hall L, Bowyer KS. 2003.** Improving prediction of the minority class in boosting. In: *European Conference on Principles of Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 107–119.
- Christoph G, Goldhammer F, Zylka J, Hartig J. 2015.** Adolescents' computer performance: the role of self-concept and motivational aspects. *Computers & Education* **81**:1–12 DOI [10.1016/j.compedu.2014.09.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.09.004).
- Collazos C, Guerrero L, Llaña M, Oetzel J. 2014.** Gender: an influence factor in the collaborative work process. In: *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on New Educational Environment (ICNEE'2002), Lugano, Switzerland, May, 2002*, 7–10.
- Cyr D, Head M, Lim E, Stibe A. 2018.** Using the elaboration likelihood model to examine online persuasion through website design. *Information & Management* **55**(7):807–821 DOI [10.1016/j.im.2018.03.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2018.03.009).
- Czaja S, Lee C. 2007.** The impact of aging on access to technology. *Universal Access in the Information Society* **5**(4):341–349 DOI [10.1007/s10209-006-0060-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-006-0060-x).
- Czerwinski M, Tan D, Robertson G. 2002.** Women take a wider view. In: *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 195–202 DOI [10.1145/503376.503412](https://doi.org/10.1145/503376.503412).

- Davis J, Goadrich M. 2006.** The relationship between precision-recall and ROC curves. In: *Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Machine Learning*, 233–240 DOI [10.1145/1143844.1143874](https://doi.org/10.1145/1143844.1143874).
- De Andrés J, Pariente B, Gonzalez-Rodriguez M, Fernandez Lanvin D. 2015.** Towards an automatic user profiling system for online information sites: identifying demographic determining factors. *Online Information Review* **39(1)**:61–80 DOI [10.1108/oir-06-2014-0134](https://doi.org/10.1108/oir-06-2014-0134).
- Dichiu D, Rancea I. 2016.** Using machine learning algorithms for author profiling in social media. In: *CLEF (Working Notes)*, 58–863.
- Dickinson A, Arnott J, Prior S. 2007.** Methods for human–computer interaction research with older people. *Behaviour & Information Technology* **26**:343–352 DOI [10.1080/01449290601176948](https://doi.org/10.1080/01449290601176948).
- Domingos PMA. 1999.** MetaCost: a general method for making classifiers cost-sensitive. In: *Proceedings of the Fifth ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, 155–164 DOI [10.1145/312129.312220](https://doi.org/10.1145/312129.312220).
- Fernandez-Lanvin D, Andres-Suarez J, Gonzalez-Rodriguez M, Pariente-Martinez B. 2018.** The dimension of age and gender as user model demographic factors for automatic personalization in e-commerce sites. *Computer Standards & Interfaces* **59**:1–9 DOI [10.1016/j.csi.2018.02.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csi.2018.02.001).
- Fisk A, Czaja S, Rogers W, Charness N, Sharit J. 2005.** *Designing for older adults: principles and creative human factors approaches*. Netherlands: International Society for Gerontechnology.
- Flach P. 2003.** The geometry of ROC space: understanding machine learning metrics through ROC isometrics. In: *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML-03)*, 194–201.
- Floh A, Madlberger M. 2013.** The role of atmospheric cues in online impulse-buying behavior. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications* **12(6)**:425–439 DOI [10.1016/j.elerap.2013.06.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elerap.2013.06.001).
- Freudenthal D. 2001.** Age differences in the performance of information retrieval tasks. *Behaviour & Information Technology* **20**:9–22 DOI [10.1080/01449290110049745](https://doi.org/10.1080/01449290110049745).
- Friedman J, Hastie T, Tibshirani R. 2000.** Additive logistic regression: a statistical view of boosting (with discussion and a rejoinder by the authors). *The Annals of Statistics* **28(2)**:337–407 DOI [10.1214/aos/1016218223](https://doi.org/10.1214/aos/1016218223).
- Ghrban Z, El Abbadi NK. 2023.** Gender and age estimation from human faces based on deep learning techniques: a review. *International Journal of Computing and Digital Systems* **12(3)**:245–260.
- Gil-López C, Guixeres J, Moghaddasi M, Khatri J, Marín-Morales J, Alcañiz M. 2023.** Recognizing shopper demographics from behavioral responses in a virtual reality store. *Virtual Reality* **27(3)**:1021–1035 DOI [10.1007/s10055-023-00767-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-023-00767-2).
- Gomez J-C, Moreno J, Ibarra-Manzano M, Almanza-Ojeda D. 2024.** Reconstructive classification for age and gender identification in social networks. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems* **11(2)**:789–801 DOI [10.1109/tcss.2023.3267766](https://doi.org/10.1109/tcss.2023.3267766).
- Gong R, Kieras D. 1994.** A validation of the GOMS model methodology in the development of a specialized, commercial software application. In: *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems-Proceedings*, 351–357 DOI [10.1145/191666.191782](https://doi.org/10.1145/191666.191782).
- Guiard Y, Olafsdottir H, Perrault S. 2011.** Fitt’s law as an explicit time/error trade-off. In: *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1619–1628 DOI [10.1145/1978942.1979179](https://doi.org/10.1145/1978942.1979179).

- Haque A, Sadeghzadeh J, Khatibi A. 2006.** Identifying potentiality online sales in Malaysia: a study on customer relationships online shopping. *Journal of Applied Business Research (JABR)* 22(4):119–130 DOI 10.19030/jabr.v22i4.1420.
- Hernández-Orallo J, Flach P, Ferri CA. 2012.** A unified view of performance metrics: translating threshold choice into expected classification loss. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 13:2813–2869.
- Hill R, Dickinson A, Arnott J, Gregor P, McIver L. 2011.** Older web users' eye movements: experience counts. In: *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1151–1160 DOI 10.1145/1978942.1979115.
- Hosseini M, Tammimy Z. 2016.** Recognizing users gender in social media using linguistic features. *Computers in Human Behavior* 56(2454):192–197 DOI 10.1016/j.chb.2015.11.049.
- Inkpen K. 2001.** Drag-and-drop versus point-and-click mouse interaction styles for children. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)* 8(1):1–33 DOI 10.1145/371127.371146.
- Japkowicz N, Stephen S. 2002.** The class imbalance problem: a systematic study. *Intelligent Data Analysis* 6(5):429–449 DOI 10.3233/ida-2002-6504.
- John B, Vera A, Matessa M, Freed M, Remington R. 2002.** Automating CPM-GOMS. In: *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 147–154 DOI 10.1145/503376.503404.
- Kambil A, Eselius E, Monteiro KFv. 2000.** The quick way to start web businesses. *MIT Sloan Management Review* 41:55.
- Khan S, Rana Z. 2019.** Evaluating performance of software defect prediction models using area under precision-recall curve (AUC-PR). In: *2nd International Conference on Advancements in Computational Sciences (ICACS)*, 1–6 DOI 10.23919/ICACS.2019.8689135.
- Khan M, Sohrab M, Yousuf M. 2020.** Customer gender prediction system on hierarchical e-commerce data. *Beni-Suef University Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences* 9(1):2034 DOI 10.1186/s43088-020-0035-7.
- Kuhtz-Buschbeck J, Stolze H, Jöhnk K, Boczek-Funcke A, Illert M. 1998.** Development of prehension movements in children: a kinematic study. *Experimental Brain Research* 122(4):424–432 DOI 10.1007/s002210050530.
- Lee M. 2009.** Understanding the behavioural intention to play online games. *Online Information Review* 33(5):849–872 DOI 10.1108/14684520911001873.
- Ling C, Huang J, Zhang HA. 2003.** A better measure than accuracy in comparing learning algorithms. In: *Conference of the Canadian Society for Computational Studies of Intelligence*, 329–341 DOI 10.1007/3-540-44886-1_25.
- Ling C, Li C. 1998.** Data mining for direct marketing: problems and solutions. In: *Kdd*, 73–79.
- Liu W, Chawla SA. 2011.** A quadratic mean based supervised learning model for managing data skewness. In: *Proceedings of the 2011 SIAM International Conference on Data Mining*, 188–198.
- Lu S, Zhao M, Zhang H, Zhang C, Wang W, Wang H. 2015.** Genderpredictor: a method to predict gender of customers from e-commerce website. In: *IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conference on Web Intelligence and Intelligent Agent Technology (WI-IAT)*, 13–16 DOI 10.1109/WI-IAT.2015.106.
- MacKenzie I, Sellen A, Buxton WA. 1991.** A comparison of input devices in element pointing and dragging tasks. In: *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 161–166 DOI 10.1145/108844.108868.

- Metter E, Conwit R, Tobin J, Fozard J. 1997.** Age-associated loss of power and strength in the upper extremities in women and men. *The Journals of Gerontology Series A: Biological Sciences and Medical Sciences* 52(5):B267–B276 DOI 10.1093/gerona/52a.5.b267.
- Morrell ROa. 2001.** *Older adults, health information and the World Wide Web*. Oxfordshire: Psychology Press.
- Muntean M, Vlean H, Ilean I, Rotar C. 2010.** Improving classification with support vector machine for unbalanced data. *2010 IEEE International Conference On Automation, Quality and Testing, Robotics (AQTR)* 3:1–6 DOI 10.1109/aqtr.2010.5520736.
- Nap H, De Greef H, Bouwhuis D. 2005.** Access for all by cognitive engineering. *Gerontechnology* 3:258 DOI 10.4017/gt.2005.03.04.143.00.
- Neerincx M, Lindenberg J, Rypkema J, Van Besouw SA. 2000.** Practical cognitive theory of web-navigation: explaining age-related performance differences. In: *Position Paper CHI, 2000 Workshop Basic Research Symposium*.
- Nguyen D, Gravel R, Trieschnigg D, Meder T. 2013.** Tweetgenie: automatic age prediction from tweets. *ACM SIGWEB Newsletter* 2013:1–6 DOI 10.1145/2528272.2528276.
- Oyewole S, Haight J. 2011.** Determination of optimal paths to task goals using expert system based on GOMS model. *Computers in Human Behavior* 27(2):823–833 DOI 10.1016/j.chb.2010.11.007.
- O'Connor K, Golder S, Weissenbacher D, Klein A, Magge A, Gonzalez-Hernandez G. 2024.** Methods and annotated data sets used to predict the gender and age of twitter users: scoping review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research* 26(1):e48921 DOI 10.1101/2022.12.06.22283170.
- Pariente Martínez B. 2020.** Automatic user modelling through demographic analysis of user interaction. Tesis doctoral. doctorado en informática, Universidad de Oviedo. Acceso abierto.
- Pariente-Martinez B, Gonzalez-Rodriguez M, Fernandez-Lanvin D, De Andres-Suarez J. 2016.** Measuring the role of age in user performance during interaction with computers. *Universal Access in the Information Society* 15(2):237–247 DOI 10.1007/s10209-014-0388-6.
- Park S, Woo J. 2019.** Gender classification using sentiment analysis and deep learning in a health web forum. *Applied Sciences* 9(6):1249 DOI 10.3390/app9061249.
- Pazzani M, Billsus D. 2007.** Content-based recommendation systems. In: Brusilovsky P, Kobsa A, Nejdl W, eds. *The Adaptive Web: Methods and Strategies of Web Personalization*. Vol. 4321. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag, 325–341 DOI 10.1007/978-3-540-72079-9_10.
- Phillips J, Triggs T. 2001.** Characteristics of cursor trajectories controlled by the computer mouse. *Ergonomics* 44(5):527–536 DOI 10.1080/00140130121560.
- Provost FJ, Fawcett T, Kohavi R. 1998.** The case against accuracy estimation while comparing induction algorithms. In: *ICML Conference*, 445–453.
- Rohr L. 2006.** Gender-specific movement strategies using a computer-pointing task. *Journal of Motor Behavior* 38(6):431–137 DOI 10.3200/jmbr.38.6.431-137.
- Rosati L. 2013.** How to design interfaces for choice: hick-hyman law and classification for information architecture. In: *Proceedings of the International UDC Seminar*, 121–134.
- Salthouse T. 1984.** Effects of age and skill in typing. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General* 113(3):345–371 DOI 10.1037/0096-3445.113.3.345.
- Sayers H. 2004.** Desktop virtual environments: a study of navigation and age. *Interacting with Computers* 16(5):939–956 DOI 10.1016/j.intcom.2004.05.003.
- Schiaffino S, Amandi AI. 2009.** Intelligent user profiling. *Artificial Intelligence an International Perspective: an International Perspective* 5640:193–216 DOI 10.1007/978-3-642-03226-4_11.

- Schneider D, Anderson JA. 2011.** Memory-based model of hick's law. *Cognitive Psychology* 62(3):193–222 DOI 10.1016/j.cogpsych.2010.11.001.
- Schrepp MG. 2010.** GOMS analysis as a tool to investigate the usability of web units for disabled users. *Universal Access in the Information Society* 9(1):77–86 DOI 10.1007/s10209-009-0155-2.
- Sebora T, Lee S, Sukasame N. 2009.** Critical success factors for e-commerce entrepreneurship: an empirical study of Thailand. *Small Business Economics* 32(3):303–316 DOI 10.1007/s11187-007-9091-9.
- Sobieraj S, Krämer N. 2020.** Similarities and differences between genders in the usage of computer with different levels of technological complexity. *Computers in Human Behavior* 104(7–8):106145 DOI 10.1016/j.chb.2019.09.021.
- Stubbs N, Fernandez J, Glenn W. 1993.** Normative data on joint ranges of motion of 25- to 54-year-old males. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* 12(4):265–272 DOI 10.1016/0169-8141(93)90096-v.
- Swami CP. 2024.** A framework for gait-based user demography estimation using inertial sensors. ArXiv DOI 10.48550/arXiv.2402.09761.
- Tan D, Czerwinski M, Robertson G. 2003.** Women go with the (optical) flow. In: *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 209–215 DOI 10.1145/642611.642649.
- Tang Y, Zhang Y, Chawla N, Krasser S. 2008.** Svms modeling for highly imbalanced classification. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part B (Cybernetics)* 39(1):281–288 DOI 10.1109/tsmcb.2008.2002909.
- Tsimperidis I, Yucel C, Katos V. 2021.** Age and gender as cyber attribution features in keystroke dynamic-based user classification processes. *Electronics* 10(7):835 DOI 10.3390/electronics10070835.
- Tullis T. 2007.** Older adults and the web: lessons learned from eye-tracking. In: *Universal Access in Human Computer Interaction. Coping with Diversity*, 1030–1039.
- Turban E, King D, Lee J, Viehland D. 2002.** *Electronic commerce: a managerial perspective*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Vines J, Pritchard G, Wright P, Olivier P, Brittain KA. 2015.** An Age-Old Problem: Examining the discourses of ageing in hci and strategies for future research. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)* 22(2):1–27 DOI 10.1145/2696867.
- Wahlström J, Svensson J, Hagberg M, Johnson P. 2000.** Differences between work methods and gender in computer mouse use. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health* 26:390–397 DOI 10.5271/sjweh.559.
- Walker N, Philbin D, Fisk A. 1997.** Age-related differences in movement control: adjusting submovement structure to optimize performance. *The Journals of Gerontology Series B: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences* 52(1):P40–P53 DOI 10.1093/geronb/52b.1.p40.
- Weiser E. 2000.** Gender differences in internet use patterns and internet application preferences: a two-sample comparison. *Cyberpsychology and Behavior* 3(2):167–178 DOI 10.1089/109493100316012.
- West R, Macdougall KT. 2014.** The macro-architecture hypothesis: Modifying newell's system levels to include macro-cognition. *Biologically Inspired Cognitive Architectures* 8(4):140–149 DOI 10.1016/j.bica.2014.03.009.
- West R, Pronovost S. 2009.** Modeling sgoms in ACT-R: linking macro- and microcognition. *Journal of Cognitive Engineering and Decision Making* 3(2):194–207 DOI 10.1518/155534309x441853.

- Xie B. 2003.** Older adults, computers, and the internet: future directions. *Gerontechnology* 2:289–305 DOI [10.4017/gt.2003.02.04.002.00](https://doi.org/10.4017/gt.2003.02.04.002.00).
- Xu H, Zou X, Wang H. 2006.** Consumers' attitudes of e-commerce in China. *Issues in Information Systems* 7:202.
- Yang Y, Al-Garadi M, Love J, Perrone J, Sarker A. 2021.** Automatic gender detection in twitter profiles for health-related cohort studies. *JAMIA Open* 4(3):231 DOI [10.1101/2021.01.06.21249350](https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.01.06.21249350).
- Zhai S. 2004.** Characterizing computer input with fitts' law parameters—the information and non-information aspects of pointing. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 61(6):791–809 DOI [10.1016/j.ijhcs.2004.09.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2004.09.006).